

FLOW INDUCED MICROSTRUCTURE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: Flow-induced alignment of the dispersed phase of a composite material during processing determines the local microstructure and, thereby, the mechanical and transport properties of the final product. Model predictions of the microstructure are often based on low-order statistical properties of Smoluchowski's equation for the orientation distribution function. A second-order moment equation relates the orientation dyad to the local flow field and the orientation tetrad. Unfortunately, this approach for predicting the microstructure has been limited by the absence of a practical and accurate closure model for the orientation tetrad. This research examines flow-induced alignment of fiber suspensions and liquid crystalline polymers by using a closure approximation that retains the six-fold symmetry and six-fold projection properties of the exact orientation tetrad. In the absence of deformation, the theory predicts multiple equilibrium states. In the presence of a homogeneous shear flow, the orientation director shows periodic behavior at relatively high concentration of the dispersed phase.

KEYWORDS: Liquid crystalline polymers, orientation statistics, closure approximation, equilibrium states, flow induced alignment, simple shear.

INTRODUCTION

The prediction of orientation statistics of multiphase materials during processing has practical implications inasmuch as the microstructure dramatically influences the mechanical and transport properties of composite materials and blends [1,2]. Thus, flow-induced alignment of the dispersed phase has a significant impact on the development of new composite materials that use either short fibers as a reinforcement phase or liquid crystalline polymers as a continuous phase.

Model predictions of low-order statistical properties characteristic of the microstructure are often based on a moment equation for the orientation dyad $\langle \underline{p} \underline{p} \rangle$. The unit vector \underline{p} represents the instantaneous orientation of a constituent component of the dispersed phase. The solution to the second-order moment equation for $\langle \underline{p} \underline{p} \rangle$ requires knowledge of the local flow field as well as a closure model for the orientation tetrad $\langle \underline{p} \underline{p} \underline{p} \underline{p} \rangle$. Unfortunately, the widespread use of this approach for the microstructure has been limited by the absence of a practical and accurate closure model that relates the dispersed phase orientation tetrad (fourth-order moment) to the dispersed phase orientation dyad (second-order moment).

Petty and his colleagues [3-7] have recently developed a new closure approximation that retains the six-fold symmetry and projection (contraction) properties of the exact orientation tetrad. The salient features of the new theory are summarized below for a class of lyotropic liquid crystalline polymers governed by a Meier-Saupe excluded volume potential and Brownian motion in the absence of an external field [1].

MICROSTRUCTURE THEORY

The unit vector \underline{p} is defined to be oriented parallel to the major axis of a rigid molecule or fiber. The fraction of polymer molecules having orientation coordinates on the unit sphere in the range $0 \leq \theta \leq \theta + \Delta\theta$ and $0 \leq \phi \leq \phi + \Delta\phi$ is given by

$$P\{0 \leq \theta \leq \theta + \Delta\theta, 0 \leq \phi \leq \phi + \Delta\phi\} = \Psi(\theta, \phi, t) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi. \quad (1)$$

The orientation distribution function $\Psi(\theta, \phi, t)$ is governed by the Smoluchowski's equation [1,2]:

$$\frac{D\Psi}{Dt} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \underline{p}} \cdot [(\underline{p} \cdot \nabla \underline{u} - \underline{p}\underline{p}\underline{p} : \nabla \underline{u}) \Psi] = \bar{D}_R \frac{\partial}{\partial \underline{p}} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{p}} + \Psi \frac{\partial}{\partial \underline{p}} \left(\frac{\Delta U_{MS}}{k_B T} \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

subject to the condition that

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \Psi(\theta, \phi, t) \sin\theta d\theta d\phi = 1. \quad (3)$$

\bar{D}_R is the rotary diffusion coefficient (1/time) and ΔU_{MS} is the Maier-Saupe potential for the excluded volume,

$$\Delta U_{MS} = -\frac{3}{2} U k_B T \underline{p} \underline{p} : (\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle - \frac{1}{3} \underline{I}). \quad (4)$$

The Maier-Saupe (MS-) potential depends explicitly on the microstructure and implicitly on the volume fraction of the dispersed phase through the phenomenological coefficient U .

Low-order moments of the orientation distribution function are used to characterize the microstructure of fiber suspensions and complex fluids such as liquid crystalline polymers. The second moment, or orientation dyad, is defined as follows:

$$\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \underline{p}\underline{p} \Psi(\underline{p}, t) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi. \quad (5)$$

An equation for $\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle$ can be written as [1,2,3]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D \langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle}{Dt} = & +(\nabla \underline{u})^T \cdot \langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle + \langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle \cdot \nabla \underline{u} - 2 : \langle \underline{p}\underline{p}\underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle : \underline{S} \\ & - 6 \bar{D}_R [(\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle - \frac{1}{3} \underline{I}) - U(\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle \cdot \langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle - \langle \underline{p}\underline{p}\underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle : \langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle)] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In the above equation, $\nabla \underline{u}$ is the velocity gradient. For liquid crystalline polymers, it is noteworthy that the orientation tetrad directly impacts the microstructure by coupling with both the orientation dyad and the strain rate,

$$\langle \underline{pppp} \rangle : \langle \underline{pp} \rangle \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \underline{pppp} \rangle : \underline{S} .$$

A preclosure for the orientation tetrad (FSQ-preclosure) is given by

$$\langle \underline{pppp} \rangle = (1 - C_2) \langle \underline{pppp} \rangle_1 + C_2 \langle \underline{pppp} \rangle_2 \quad \text{where} \quad (7)$$

$$\langle \underline{pppp} \rangle_1 = -\frac{1}{35} S[\underline{I}, \underline{I}] + \frac{1}{7} S[\underline{I}, \langle \underline{pp} \rangle], \quad \text{and} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \underline{pppp} \rangle_2 = \frac{2}{35} \langle \underline{pp} \rangle : \langle \underline{pp} \rangle S[\underline{I}, \underline{I}] \\ + S[\langle \underline{pp} \rangle \cdot \langle \underline{pp} \rangle, \langle \underline{pp} \rangle \cdot \langle \underline{pp} \rangle] - \frac{2}{7} S[\underline{I}, \langle \underline{pp} \rangle \cdot \langle \underline{pp} \rangle] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In the above equations, the result of the operation $S[\underline{A}, \underline{B}]$ is a fully symmetric tetradic-valued operator formed from the two indicated symmetric dyadic-valued operators. In this presentation, it is assumed that $C_2 = 1/3$, \bar{D}_R is constant, and U is constant for all microstructures. The details are given in Petty *et al.* [3].

The foregoing theory seeks a balance between the flow alignment process and the rotary diffusion process in orientation space. U is a dimensionless measure of the strength of the Maier-Saupe potential and accounts for the excluded volume self-alignment process on the rotary diffusive flux. The dimensionless time τ ($\equiv 6D_{RT}$), the Peclet number Pe ($\equiv \dot{\gamma}/6D_r$), and the dimensionless group U govern the relaxation of the microstructure. The invariants II_b and III_b of the structure tensor \underline{b} , defined by

$$\underline{b} \equiv \langle \underline{pp} \rangle - \frac{1}{3} \underline{I} \quad , \quad II_b \equiv \text{tr}(\underline{b} \cdot \underline{b} \cdot \underline{b}) \quad , \quad III_b \equiv \text{tr}(\underline{b} \cdot \underline{b} \cdot \underline{b}), \quad (14)$$

must remain in the realizability domain illustrated by Figure 1 inasmuch as the eigenvalues of the orientation dyad are non-negative.

RESULTS

For $Pe = 0$ and $U > 5$, the equilibrium states predicted by the FSQ-model are anisotropic. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of these states on the invariant diagram for $5 < U < 10$. The parameter α , defined in the figure caption, is used to characterize the degree of orientation of the prolate and oblate equilibrium states. Figure 3 shows that the FSQ-model predicts multiple steady states for $4.654 < U < 5$. This result corrects an earlier conclusion that the FSQ-model with $C_2 = 1/3$ does not yield a subcritical equilibrium instability [see 4, 5].

Although an isotropic microstructure satisfies the steady-state moment equation for all values of U , a dynamic analysis for the orientation dyad shows that the isotropic state is stable for $U < 4.656$ and unstable for $U > 5.000$. For $4.654 < U < 5.000$, three steady states are predicted: a conditionally stable isotropic state, an unstable anisotropic state, and a conditionally stable

anisotropic state. The quadratic form associated with the anisotropic microstructure has a prolate shape. The FSQ-model with $C_2 = 1/3$ and $Pe = 0$ is consistent with the qualitative behavior of lyotropic liquid crystalline polymers and other theories for LCP microstructure [1,2]

The FSQ-closure predicts a tumbling microstructure for $Pe = 15$ and $U = 21$ (see Figure 4). Figure 5 shows the angle between the director and the flow direction as well as the eigenvalue associated with the director. Although the orientation director tumbles around the fixed flow direction, $\underline{n}(t)$ remains approximately aligned (i.e., $\chi \cong 0$) with the velocity for most of the cycle before rotating rapidly. The dimensionless time in Figure 5 is $6D_R t$; therefore, for $Pe = 15$ and $U = 21$, the theory predicts that the tumbling period is on the order of $1/D_R$. Figure 6 shows the projection of the tumbling orbit on the realizability diagram.

CONCLUSIONS

The FSQ-closure for the orientation tetrad provides a realizable closure to the moment equation governing the orientation dyad for liquid crystalline polymers governed by a Meier-Saupe excluded volume potential. The new closure predicts multiple equilibrium states for $Pe = 0$; periodic states for $Pe > 0$; and a transition to a self-aligning steady-state regime for large values of Pe and U . For $Pe > 0$ and $U < 17$, the director approaches a steady-state offset from the flow direction (i.e., $\chi > 0$).

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Figure 1. Model Independent Realizable Orientation States [3]

Point A ($II_b = 2/3$ and $III_b = 2/9$) corresponds to a nematic microstructure with $\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle = \underline{e}_3 \underline{e}_3$. Boundary B contains planar anisotropic microstructures for which the eigenvalues of $\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle$ are $(0, 1 - \lambda_3, \lambda_3)$ with $1/2 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1$.

Point C ($II_b = 1/6$ and $III_b = -1/36$) corresponds to a planar isotropic microstructure with $2\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle = \underline{e}_2 \underline{e}_2 + \underline{e}_3 \underline{e}_3$. Boundary D contains oblate microstructures for which the eigenvalues of $\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle$ are given by $(1 - 2\lambda_3, \lambda_3, \lambda_3)$ with $1/3 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1/2$.

Point E ($II_b = 0$ and $III_b = 0$) corresponds to a three-dimensional isotropic microstructure with $3\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle = \underline{e}_1 \underline{e}_1 + \underline{e}_2 \underline{e}_2 + \underline{e}_3 \underline{e}_3$. Boundary F contains prolate microstructures for which the eigenvalues of $\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle$ are $((1 - \lambda_3)/2, (1 - \lambda_3)/2, \lambda_3)$ with $1/3 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1$. The vectors $\underline{e}_1, \underline{e}_2, \underline{e}_3$ are mutually orthonormal vectors.

Figure 2. Prolate and Oblate Equilibrium States for $5 < U < 10$ [5, 6]

Bhave *et al.*[8] used a scalar parameter α to quantify the degree of orientation for prolate and oblate microstructures. Nguyen [5] adopted this approach to characterize the equilibrium states by using the following definitions:

$$\alpha(t) \equiv + \left(\frac{3}{2} \text{II}_b \right)^{1/2}, \text{II}_b \geq 0 \text{ (prolate states), and}$$

$$\alpha(t) \equiv - \left(\frac{3}{2} \text{II}_b \right)^{1/2}, \text{II}_b \leq 0 \text{ (oblate states).}$$

A perfectly aligned state (or nematic state) corresponds to $\alpha = 1$ (see Point A on Figure 1). A planar isotropic state (see Point C on Figure 1) corresponds to $\alpha = -1/2$. A three-dimensional isotropic state (see Point E on Figure 1) corresponds to $\alpha = 0$.

Figure 3. The influence of U (x-axis) on the structure coefficient α (y-axis)

Prolate equilibrium states are predicted by the FSQ-Closure for $C_2 = 1/3$. The isotropic/prolate (IP-) transition occurs at $U = 5$ and the prolate/isotropic (PI-) transition occurs at 4.654. A branch of oblate states (not shown) bifurcates from the isotropic state at $U = 5$. The isotropic state is unstable to infinitesimal perturbations for $U > 5$. Three prolate steady states exist for $4.654 < U < 5$: a conditionally stable isotropic state; an unstable prolate state; and, a conditionally stable prolate state. The isotropic state is unconditionally stable for $U < 4.654$.

Figure 4. Microstructure transition diagram for $Pe > 0$ and $U > 0$ [4,5,6]

Figure 5. Director and eigenvalue tumbling for $Pe = 15$ and $U = 21$ [6]

The director \underline{n} of the microstructure is the eigenvector associated with the largest eigenvalue λ_3 of the orientation dyad $\langle \underline{p}\underline{p} \rangle$. An instantaneous measure of the relative alignment of the orientation director and the flow direction is given by

$$\underline{n} \cdot \frac{\underline{u}}{\|\underline{u}\|} \equiv \underline{n} \cdot \underline{e}_3 = n_3 = \cos(\chi),$$

where χ is the angle between the two unit vectors \underline{n} and \underline{e}_3 . For homogeneous shear flows, the director tends to align with the flow direction (i.e., $\cos(\chi) \equiv 1$).

Figure 6. Realizable periodic orbit for $Pe = 15$ and $U = 21$ [7]